

Original article

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THE IMPACT OF THE GIG ECONOMY ON THE HOSPITALITY SECTOR

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Abstract: *The hospitality industry is facing significant challenges such as seasonal peaks, sudden demand surges, and last-minute staff shortages, which have become major recruitment pain points. As a response to these challenges, the gig economy, based on short-term engagements and flexible forms of work, is increasingly shaping the labor market. The aim of this paper is to analyze the impact of gig economy in job mediation. Findings from previous research reveal the ambivalent impact of the gig economy. On the one hand, it enables rapid recruitment, lower hiring costs, and adaptability to seasonal demand. However, the main drawbacks for employers, include reduced quality control, weak employee loyalty, and challenges in maintaining sustainable human resource strategies. As for gig workers, although this model allows additional income and autonomy in the short term, it often leads to limited professional development and lack of benefits in the long term. In order to minimize the risks associated with these platforms, new frameworks must be introduced to safeguard all participants in the process. Therefore, gig economy may be considered a useful complementary mechanism for addressing short-term staffing needs, but not a sustainable long-term solution to employment challenges in the hospitality sector.*

Keywords: *Gig economy, hospitality, human resources, digital platforms.*